

Original Research Article

Increasing Nurse Performance through Strengthening the Effectiveness of Basic Trauma Life Support (BTCLS) Training, Teamwork and Service Leadership

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Abstract

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The purpose of this study was to find out how the performance of civil servant nurses at the West Jakarta Hospital could be improved by examining the relationship between the effectiveness of training, teamwork and service leadership with nurse performance. The population of this study were Associate of Science in Nursing (ASN) at Regional Hospitals (RSUD) in West Jakarta City totaling 597 people from 4 hospitals. The sampling technique used is a random sampling technique (proportional random sampling). Samples were taken using the Slovin formula with a sampling error rate of 5%. The results of the calculation of the number of samples are 239 people. The research method uses quantitative methods. The results show that there is a positive and very significant relationship between the effectiveness of BTCLS training and nurse performance, there is a positive and very significant relationship between teamwork and nurse performance, there is a positive and very significant relationship between service leadership with nurse performance This means that the productivity of nurses' performance in West Jakarta Hospital can be increased through strengthening the effectiveness of BTCLS training, teamwork, and service leadership variables.

Keywords: Effectiveness of BTCLS Training, Nurse Performance, Servant Leadership, Teamwork

INTRODUCTION

Nurses as one of the health workers in hospitals play an important role in achieving health development goals. The success of health services depends on the participation of nurses in providing quality nursing care for patients. According to Zheng et al. (2020) presence of nurses on duty 24 hours to serve patients, as well as the number of nurses who dominate health workers in hospitals, which is around 40-60%. Therefore, the hospital must have good performing nurses who will support the hospital's performance so that customer or patient satisfaction can be achieved. Nurse performance is a nurse's activity in implementing as well as possible an authority, duty and responsibility in the context of achieving the goals of the profession's main tasks and

realizing the goals and objectives of the organizational unit. Nurse performance is actually the same as work performance in the company. According to Abedinya et al. (2020) Nurses want to measure their performance based on objective standards that are open and can be communicated. If nurses are cared for and rewarded with superior rewards, they will be more motivated to achieve higher levels of achievement. Individual characteristics related to nurse performance are education, training, promotion, career path, length of work, reward system, salary, allowances, incentives and bonuses. nurse performance. Servant leadership can be one of the factors that cause a person's performance. According to Yang et al. (2021), the behavior of a leader who prioritizes

service to others, with the aim that the individuals served can grow, be healthy, independent (autonomous), and have a spirit of service. This will also affect one's performance.

Through training or through learning assignments, nurses can improve their competence and insight, and these nurses will have responsibility and loyalty in working optimally, so that they can carry out their duties as nurses properly. According to Yang et al. (2021); Zheng et al. (2020), training is one of the important components in the development of human resources (HR) to improve knowledge, skills and attitudes which are expected to improve institutional performance in the face of change and external competition. Another factor that can be related to the performance of nurses is teamwork. Nurses' performance will increase if in life in hospitals they have good teamwork and leadership, a cultured environment conducive to good spiritual support will raise their own awareness which will certainly be good and cooperative synergy in achieving the goals of hospitals together. The teamwork factor in the work environment is related to performance. The teamwork that a person has can help him complete his work well, produce new works or innovations and can increase one's productivity and performance.

Based on the explanation above, it can be seen that there are many factors related to the performance of a nurse. In this study, it will be limited to the three variables related to the performance of nurses, namely training, teamwork and service leadership. In addition to this phenomenon, the performance of nurses needs to be investigated because health workers themselves are multidimensional professions, both aspects of professional competence, namely cognitive, psychomotor and affective; also psychological, moral, ethical and so on. All of these aspects require high nurse performance so that their work can be done well. Nurses with good performance will carry out their duties and functions well which has implications for the quality of good nurse services. This can be realized if the leadership element that regulates the institution's management, human resources itself in terms of service leadership and teamwork, as well as other factors are considered and handled properly. Based on these statements, nurses' performance was obtained with indicators: 1. Quality of work; 2. Quantity of work and attendance; 3. Supervision results; 4. Quality of Service to the Environment. The facts generated are based on the results of a preliminary survey using a questionnaire . 34% of nurses are not optimal in the quality of work. 2). 31% of nurses are not optimal in the quantity of work and attendance. 32% of nurses are not optimal in the results of supervision. There are 34% nurses who are not optimal in the quality of service to the environment

The purpose of this study was to find out how the performance of civil servant nurses at the West Jakarta Hospital could be improved by examining the relationship

between the effectiveness of training, teamwork and service leadership with nurse performance. namely the identification of the strength of the relationship between the effectiveness of training with nurse performance. The strength of the relationship between teamwork and nurse performance. The strength of the relationship between servant leadership and nurse performance. The strength of the relationship between the effectiveness of training and teamwork together with the performance of nurses. The strength of the relationship between training effectiveness and service leadership together with nurse performance. The strength of the relationship between teamwork and service leadership goes hand in hand with nurse performance. The strength of the relationship between the effectiveness of training, teamwork and service leadership together with nurse performance

METHOD

This research was conducted at Regional General Hospitals throughout the City of West Jakarta, as many as 4 hospitals, and the research was carried out for 6 months covering from proposal preparation until research data was obtained and processed regarding Nurse Performance, Effectiveness of Training, Team Work, and Service Leadership. The method used in this research is the survey method, the Sequential Explanatory Method, with a correlational approach in the variables contained in it, and SITOREM analysis is carried out. In this study, there are three independent variables, namely Effectiveness of Training (X1), Teamwork (X2), and Servant Leadership (X3) and the dependent variable is Nurse Performance (Y). The relationship between each independent variable and the dependent variable is presented in the problem constellation as shown in Figure 1 below.

Gambar 1 : Konstelasi penelitian

X1: Training Effectiveness, X2: Teamwork, X3: Serving Leadership, Y: Nurse Performance.

Table 1. Summary Analysis of Significance Test Variance Regression Equation

Hypothesis	Regression	Significant		Conclusion
		Coef. Correlation	Coef. Determination	
Y-X1	$\hat{Y} = 96.594 + 0.273 X_1$	0.715	0.538 /53.8%	Significant
Y-X2	$\hat{Y} = 73.324 + 0.495 X_2$	0.849	0.720 /84.9%	Significant
Y-X3	$\hat{Y} = 85.313 + 3.732 X_3$	0.674	0.487 /48.7%	Significant
Y-X1-2	$\hat{Y} = 72.551 + 0.105X_1 + 0.379 X_2$	0.845	0.715 /71.5%	Significant
Y-X1-3	$Y = 77.806 + 0.189X_1 + 0.232X_3$	0.719	0.626 /62.6%	Significant
Y-X2-3	$\hat{Y} = 63.051 + 0.391X_2 + 0.176X_3$	0.860	0.740 /74.0%	Significant
Y-X123	$\hat{Y} = 63.949 + 0.076X_1 + 0.322X_2 + X_3$	0.871	0.759 /75.9%	Significant

The population of this study were all nurses with the status of permanent employees at hospitals in the Madya City area of West Jakarta as many as 579 people. Sampling is a proportional random technique while determining the number of samples using the Taro Yamane model to obtain 239 samples. The data analysis technique in this study fully uses the help of SPSS version 20 software including descriptive statistical analysis, data analysis requirements testing including normality test, homogeneity test and linearity test and hypothesis testing including simple and multiple regression tests, simple and multiple correlation tests.

Referring to the theory and previous research as well as the framework of thinking that has been described previously, the main hypothesis proposed in this study is "the structure of the relationship between variables related to the performance of nurses in DKI Jakarta Province." Those variables are BTCLS Training Effectiveness, Teamwork and Servant Leadership." Based on the main hypothesis, this research hypothesis is formulated as follows:

1. There is a relationship between the effectiveness of the training and the performance of nurses, so that strengthening the effectiveness of training can improve the performance of nurses.
2. There is a relationship between teamwork and nurse performance, so that strengthening teamwork can improve nurse performance.
3. There is a relationship between service leadership and nurse performance, so that strengthening service leadership can improve nurse performance.
4. There is a relationship between the effectiveness of training and teamwork together with the performance of nurses so that strengthening the effectiveness of training and teamwork together can improve the performance of nurses.
5. There is a relationship between the effectiveness of training and serving leadership together with the performance of nurses so that strengthening the effectiveness of training and leadership in serving together can improve the performance of nurses.

6. There is a relationship between teamwork and serving leadership together with nurse performance so that strengthening teamwork and serving leadership together can improve nurse performance.

7. There is a relationship between the effectiveness of training, teamwork and leadership in serving together with the performance of nurses so that strengthening the effectiveness of training, teamwork and leadership in serving together can improve the performance of nurses.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Statistical Hypothesis Testing Based on the calculations obtained the equation between the variables Y and X as well as a significance test whose summary is presented in the following table 1:

Relationship between Training Effectiveness and Nurse Performance

The results of the study for the training effectiveness instrument obtained a median value of 146, far above the theoretical median of 95, indicating that the effectiveness of the training was good. On the other hand, the results of the significant correlation test between the effectiveness of the training and the performance of nurses obtained the value of $t_{count} = 15,730$ which is greater than the value of $t_{table} = 1.6525$ which indicates there is a significant relationship between the effectiveness of training and the performance of nurses.

Based on the results of the study which showed that there was a significant relationship between the effectiveness of the training and the performance of nurses. Based on the results of the research by testing the hypothesis, it is known that the simple linear correlation coefficient between the effectiveness of training and the performance of nurses (r_{y1}) is 0.715. The probability value is $0.000 < 0.05$. Meanwhile, the partial correlation between the effectiveness of training and the performance of nurses is 0.296 with a probability

value of $0.000 < 0.05$, so H_0 is rejected, so it can be concluded that the correlation coefficient is significant. Thus, this study confirms that independently there is a significant relationship between the effectiveness of training and the performance of nurses.

The results of this study also get the equation = $96.594 + 0.373 X_1$ can be used to predict nurse performance based on training effectiveness scores, it can be predicted that every 1 increase in training effectiveness scores will increase nurse performance by 0.373 times at a constant 96.594. The quantitative data above is reinforced by observational data from qualitative research which concludes that the effectiveness of qualitative training in the field has the same tendency as the effectiveness of training in quantitative research. The results of this research hypothesis test are in line with Leigh et al. (2021);Guterresa et al.. (2020) training will shape character and skills in accordance with the demands of the organization, in this case the effectiveness of Basic Trauma Cardiac Life Support (BTCLS) training. BTCLS training is needed by a nurse in every work in a hospital. The results of the training will form competent nurses' skills to carry out their duties. Competent skills supported by good teamwork will produce maximum performance. The higher the effectiveness of the training implementation, the higher the nurse's performance is predicted.

Relationship between Teamwork and Nurse Performance

The results of descriptive statistical calculations for the teamwork variable obtained a median value of 150 which was far above the theoretical median of 100, indicating that the teamwork of nurses in West Jakarta Hospital was good. On the other hand, the results of the significant correlation test between teamwork and nurse performance obtained the value of $t_{count} = 22.213$, which is greater than the value of $t_{table} = 1.6525$ which indicates there is a significant relationship between teamwork and nurse performance.

Based on the results of the simple correlation hypothesis test, it shows that there is a significant relationship between nurse teamwork and nurse performance, meaning that nurses who have good teamwork will have an impact on high performance. The strength of the relationship between teamwork and nurse performance is reflected in the correlation coefficient (r_{y2}) of 0.822. The diversity in the performance of nurses related to teamwork is reflected in the coefficient of determination of 0.675 or 67.5%, while the remaining 32.5% is influenced by other factors.

The results of this study get the equation = $73.324 + 0.495 X_2$ can be used to predict nurse performance based on teamwork scores, it can be predicted that every 1 increase in teamwork score will increase nurse

performance by 0.495 times at a constant 73.324. The quantitative data above is strengthened by data from qualitative research observations that concluded that qualitative teamwork in the field has the same tendency as teamwork in quantitative research. Based on the results of interviews, it was found that the work of nurses requires good teamwork, synergy and complementarity in serving the needs of patients requires cohesiveness and mutual need between nurses with one another. The results of this qualitative analysis indicate that teamwork affects the performance of nurses. Nurses in a service unit who have good teamwork have good performance, this can be seen from the level of community satisfaction that the researchers obtained from the interviews.

RSUD is an organization that demands every doctor, nurse or other medical officer to cooperate with each other not only in the world of work but in the social environment, humans are required to work together in building a good civilization. Teamwork is believed to be able to simplify and expedite each goal because with cooperation workloads can be shared. Cooperation carried out by a team is more effective than working individually. Many studies According Abedinya et al. (2020);Alenezi et al.. (2021) have shown that working in groups leads to greater efficiency and effectiveness and this is very different from working individually. Teamwork is the fuel that enables ordinary people to achieve extraordinary results.

Nurse performance is interpreted as one of the benchmarks of organizational success, especially in public health services, so that through a focus on improving the quality of nurses, it is hoped that the quality of service will increase. Nurses are the spearhead of services in hospitals that have high workloads and challenges that demand synergy between fellow nurses. This condition requires good teamwork which will make it easier for nurses to improve their performance in serving patients and the community. Hospitals or medical institutions that are able to build good teamwork between nurses and other medical services will provide good service to the community. Based on the description above, teamwork is one of the determining factors in improving Nurse Performance.

Relationship between Servant Leadership and Nurse Performance

The results of descriptive statistics for the service leadership variable obtained a median value of 129 which was far above the theoretical median of 95, indicating that the service leadership in West Jakarta Hospital was good. On the other hand, the results of the significant correlation test between service leadership and nurse performance obtained the value of $t_{count} = 14.037$, which is greater than the value of $t_{table} = 1.6525$ which indicates there is a significant relationship between

service leadership and nurse performance.

The results of calculations and analysis of simple correlation research show that there is a significant relationship between service leadership and nurse performance. It can be interpreted that nurses who have good personalities will have high performance. The strength of the relationship between service leadership and nurse performance is reflected in the correlation coefficient (r_{y3}) of 0.674. The diversity in nurse performance related to personality is reflected in the coefficient of determination of 0.454 or 45.4%, while the remaining 54.6% is influenced by other factors.

The conclusion of the quantitative hypothesis test above is strengthened by the observational data of qualitative research. The results of interviews with a sample of nurses from hospitals obtained answers from leaders, both room leaders and hospital managers, greatly affect the motivation of nurses at work. Interviews with research samples showed that nurse leaders (bosses) both the ward head and the hospital directors, always gave respect, care and empathy to their subordinates and focused on the career of nurses. Most nurses stated that leaders (bosses) who have an attitude of caring, empathy and understanding make them comfortable at work so that their performance increases. The results of interviews and observations of the authors can be concluded that servant leadership has a strong relationship with nurse performance.

The calculations and analysis of this study are in line with the results of Leigh et al. (2021); Guterres et al. (2020); Pawar et al. (2020); Peng et al. (2021) with the conclusion that leadership has a significant influence on the performance of nurses. Nurses are the spearhead of hospital services. with a level of work that requires fast, straightforward, carefully measured and sympathetic. This heavy workload definitely poses a high challenge in addition to a high level of stress as well. The psychological condition of nurses who are always facing patients and their families with demands for excellent service will burden many nurses who need protection from superiors with an attitude of empathy, care and being able to hear every complaint from nurses. Servant leadership is a leadership that starts from feelings of sincerity that arise from the heart to serve, put the needs of followers as a priority, get things done with others and help others in achieving a common goal. Sincere attitude in serving from superiors is a strong stimulus for nurses to work more optimally. Based on the description above, it can be concluded that service leadership is one of the determinants of the performance of nurses at the West Jakarta Hospital.

Relationship Effectiveness of Training and Teamwork with Nurse Performance

Descriptive statistical data processing for training and

teamwork effectiveness variables obtained median results of 150 and 129 which are far above the theoretical median, this illustrates that the effectiveness of training and teamwork of nurses at West Jakarta Hospital is good. The statistical descriptive results of these two independent variables are in line with the descriptive results of the dependent variable on nurse performance which also obtained a median value of 146 which is far above the theoretical media value of 80. This statistical descriptive result reflects that the effectiveness of high training and teamwork will increase the performance of nurses to be high. The test results The research hypothesis shows that there is a positive relationship between the effectiveness of training and teamwork with nurse performance, which means that the training is effective and the nurses at the West Jakarta Hospital have good teamwork, the nurse's performance will be good.

Based on the results of the research hypothesis test, the correlation coefficient value of the relationship between the effectiveness of training and service leadership with nurse performance (r_{y12}) is 0.845, with a probability value (sig) 0.000 < 0.05, H_0 is rejected, meaning that there is a relationship between the effectiveness of training and teamwork with nurse performance. Thus, this study confirms that there is a relationship between the effectiveness of training and teamwork with nurse performance. Stephen P. Robbins (2002:22) explains that effectiveness is the level of organizational achievement in the short and long term. Organizational effectiveness is the concept of effectiveness which an organization aims to produce. something that shows the level of success of management activities in achieving predetermined goals. Effective training will form characters and skills that are in accordance with the demands of the organization, in this case the effectiveness of Basic Trauma Cardiac Life Support (BTCLS) training. BTCLS training is needed by a nurse in every work in a hospital. The results of the training will form competent nurses' skills to carry out their duties. Competent skills supported by teamwork are a good combination that will produce maximum nurse performance.

The results of this study are in accordance with the theory (Kerrin & Oliver: 2002). Teamwork (teamwork) is an activity or process that includes activities to share information about the problem being faced and work together in solving the problem, which is different from the notion of teamwork (teamwork) as a process, workgroup or work team. According to Guterres et al. (2020); Pawar et al. (2020) is a group consisting of two or more people who influence each other and are interdependent who come together to achieve certain goals.

Based on the description above, the effectiveness of training and teamwork is a determining factor in improving the performance of nurses at West Jakarta

Hospital. This is reinforced by the results of qualitative research, the results of interviews and observations of the sample indicate that nurses need training to improve their competence at work. The effectiveness of the training was assessed by most nurses as effective because the training materials and techniques were in line with the expectations of the nurses.

The results of interviews with samples also showed that all nurses stated the importance of teamwork, with good teamwork making it easier for nurses to provide services to patients. Nurses are fully aware that nursing work requires good teamwork. Teamwork is important compared to training, this is because the success of training is also inseparable from cohesiveness and mutual member reminding fellow nurses of good work patterns and ways. The results of these interviews and observations are able to answer the focus on the fourth qualitative research, namely: which of the two independent variables, namely the effectiveness of training and teamwork is more dominant in relation to nurse performance, obtained information based on quantitative data through partial correlation test results which are strengthened by the data. Qualitatively, teamwork is more dominant in influencing the performance of nurses than the effectiveness of training.

The Joint Relationship of Training Effectiveness and Servant Leadership with Nurse Performance

Calculation of descriptive statistical research data for the variables of effectiveness of training and leadership in serving shows medians of 150 and 135 which are far above the theoretical median, this illustrates that the Basic Trauma Cardiac Life Support (BTCLS) training for nurses at West Jakarta Hospital is effective and the superior leadership is good. the head of the room until the directors serve sincerely to subordinates. The statistical descriptive results of these two independent variables are in line with the descriptive results of the dependent variable on nurse performance which also obtained a median value of 146, far above the theoretical median value of 80, these statistical descriptive results reflect that effective training and good service leadership will increase nurse performance to be high.

The results of hypothesis testing with the regression test of the effectiveness of training and service leadership on the performance of nurses obtained a value of $F_{count} = 197.902$ which is greater than $F_{table} = 2.65$. The results of this significance test indicate that there is a significant positive relationship between the effectiveness of training and service leadership and nurse performance. Based on the calculation results, the correlation coefficient value of the relationship between training effectiveness and service leadership with (r_{y13}) is 0.791, with a probability value (sig) $0.000 < 0.005$, then H_0 is rejected, meaning that there is a significant

relationship between the effectiveness of training and service leadership and nurse performance. Thus, this study confirms that there is a significant positive relationship between the effectiveness of training and service leadership and nurse performance.

The contribution of hospital head visionary leadership and serving leadership with nurse performance (r_{y13}) of 0.626 which can be interpreted that 62.6% of the diversity in nurse performance can be explained by the effectiveness of training and service leadership. determinants of the performance of nurses in West Jakarta Hospital. This is reinforced by the results of quantitative research that obtained general answers from most nurses stating that training is important for nurses to improve competence in work. The effectiveness of the training lies in the level of usefulness of the training to the needs of nurses, meaning that training is effective if it is made in accordance with the expectations needed by nurses. Training will be effective if the leader (superior) is able to understand the conditions and needs of nurses, for that leadership that serves with care, empathy and will be able to explore the needs and expectations of nurses so that they are able to provide fun training models and materials. Based on these results, it can be answered that the focus on the fifth qualitative research is: which of the two independent variables, namely the effectiveness of training and service leadership, which is more dominant in relation to nurse performance, obtained information based on quantitative data through partial correlation test results which are strengthened by qualitative data. That personality is more dominant in influencing the performance of nurses than the effectiveness of training. The partial correlation results show that the relationship between the effectiveness of training and nurse performance with the control variables of teamwork and service leadership has no significant effect, it can be concluded that the relationship between the service leadership variable and the nurse's performance is more dominant than the relationship between the effectiveness of training and the nurse's performance.

Joint Relationships Teamwork and Servant Leadership with Nurse Performance

Calculation of descriptive statistical research data for the variables of teamwork and service leadership shows medians of 129 and 135 which are far above the theoretical median, this illustrates that the teamwork of nurses at the West Jakarta Hospital is well formed and the leadership of superiors, both the head of the room and the directors, serves sincerely to subordinate. The statistical descriptive results of these two independent variables are in line with the descriptive results of the dependent variable on nurse performance which also obtained a median value of 146 which is far above the

theoretical median value of 80. This statistical descriptive result reflects that well-formed teamwork and good service leadership will improve nurse performance.

Based on the results of hypothesis testing with the variable regression test of teamwork and Servant Leadership with the performance of nurses, it is obtained that the value of $F_{count} = 335.978$ is greater than $F_{table} = 2.65$. The results of this significance test indicate that there is a positive relationship between teamwork and servant leadership. Servant leadership will improve nurse performance to be good.

The results showed that there was a significant positive relationship between teamwork and service leadership with nurse performance. Based on the results of the study, the correlation coefficient of the relationship between teamwork and service leadership with nurse performance (r_{y23}) was 0.860, with a probability value (sig) of $0.000 < 0.05$, then H_0 was rejected, meaning that there was a relationship between teamwork and service leadership with nurse performance. Thus, this study confirms that there is a significant positive relationship between teamwork and service leadership and nurse performance.

The correlation coefficient of 0.860 according to the Guilford category, is classified as high, which means it has a high correlation. The diversity in the performance of nurses at the West Jakarta Hospital can be explained due to the influence of teamwork and service leadership, which is obtained from the value of the coefficient of determination of 0.740, which means that 74.0% of the performance factors of nurses at the West Jakarta Hospital are jointly influenced by teamwork and service leadership.

Teamwork is about synergy, connecting with others by sharing the same vision and mission. It requires a reciprocal relationship between one individual and another, which although they have different tasks, are interrelated. Teamwork is about responsibility, about how each individual in the team has their respective duties and roles to achieve common goals. Teamwork is about perspective, namely how each individual is able to understand one another, think openly, have respect for one another, allow oneself to accept new ideas that are driven by team dynamics and be assertive in it. Teamwork is about the willingness to develop and learn, namely how each individual is able to ignore the ego of the self to cooperate with others and admit that oneself is not perfect by giving room to learn from others. Servant leadership is a leadership that starts from a sincere feeling that arises from the heart to serve, placing the needs of followers as a priority, getting things done with others and helping others in achieving a common goal. Servant leaders are able to provide empathy, care and focus on the career advancement of subordinates. Leaders who serve will provide a sense of comfort and security from subordinates. According Permana et al. (2021); Purwanto et al. (2020); Yang et al. (2020);

Yang et al. (2021); Zheng et al. (2020)

Good teamwork will form synergies in work, coordination of mutual deficiencies between colleagues is the key to the success of a team. Good teamwork supported by servant leadership from superiors will increase synergy in work which will lead to improved performance of nurses. Based on the description above, the effectiveness of training, teamwork and service leadership is a determining factor in improving the performance of nurses at the West Jakarta Hospital. This is reinforced by the results of quantitative research and focuses on the sixth qualitative research, namely: which of the two independent variables, namely teamwork and personality, is more dominant in relation to Nurse Performance, obtained information based on quantitative data through a partial correlation test which is strengthened by the data. Qualitatively, service leadership has a more dominant relationship with nurse performance than teamwork, although both significantly determine the relationship with nurse performance.

Joint Relationship Effectiveness of Training, Teamwork and Servant Leadership with Nurse Performance

Based on the results of hypothesis testing with variable regression test Effectiveness of Training, Teamwork and Servant Leadership with Nurse Performance, the value of $F_{count} = 246.809$ is greater than $F_{table} = 2.65$. The results of this significance test indicate that there is a positive relationship between the effectiveness of training, teamwork and service leadership with nurse performance. It means that the Basic Trauma Cardiac Life Support (BTCLS) training for nurses at the West Jakarta Hospital is running effectively, the teamwork formed between nurses and the leadership of superiors, both the head of the room and the directors serving sincerely to subordinates, is able to improve the performance of nurses at the West Jakarta Hospital, which continues to increase from time to time.

The results showed that there was a significant positive relationship between the effectiveness of training, teamwork, and service leadership with nurse performance. Based on the results of hypothesis testing, the correlation coefficient of the relationship between the effectiveness of training, teamwork, and service leadership with nurse performance (r_{y123}) is 0.871, with a probability value (sig) of $0.000 < 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected, meaning that there is a significant positive relationship between training effectiveness, teamwork, and servant leadership with nurse performance. Thus, this study confirms that there is a significant relationship between the effectiveness of training, teamwork, and service leadership with nurse performance.

The correlation coefficient of 0.871 according to the Guilford category, is classified as high, which means it

has a high correlation. The diversity in the performance of nurses at the West Jakarta Hospital which can be explained due to the effect of the effectiveness of training, teamwork, and service leadership. The contribution of the effectiveness of training, teamwork, and service leadership to the nurse's performance (r^2_{y123}) is 0.759 which can be interpreted that 75.9% of the diversity in the nurse's performance can be explained by the effectiveness of training, teamwork and service leadership.

The performance of nurses is a form of excellent service whose success rate depends on the satisfaction of the patient, on the other hand the performance of nurses must meet the operational standards of health services that have been determined by the health department. The performance of nurses will be optimal if the skills and competencies of nurses are in accordance with the standards, this can be fulfilled by the effectiveness of Basic Trauma Cardiac Life Support (BTCLS) training. According Abedinya et al. (2020); Alenezi et al. (2021); Elche et al. (2020); Hussain et al.(2020); Leigh et al. (2021); Guterresa et al. (2020) Nurses who have passed the training will have the skills and competencies to work optimally if they are supported by good teamwork. The effectiveness of training and good teamwork will be realized by the success of a leader who is attentive, caring, considerate and focused on the progress of others, who always listens and pays attention to every need from nurses (subordinates).

Based on the description above, the effectiveness of training, teamwork and service leadership is a determining factor for the performance of nurses in West Jakarta Hospital. This is reinforced by the results of quantitative research and focuses on the sixth qualitative research, namely: which of the three independent variables is more dominant in relation to nurse performance.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of data analysis and hypothesis testing in this study, it can be concluded Based on the results of the analysis of interviews and observations, it can be concluded that there is a significant positive relationship between the effectiveness of training and the performance of nurses, this is revealed from the respondents (nurses) stating that training is needed to improve competence at work. There is a significant positive relationship between teamwork and nurse performance. Good teamwork is able to improve the performance of nurses, it can be concluded that there is a significant positive relationship between teamwork and nurse performance. It shows a positive relationship between service leadership and nurse performance. The results of the analysis from interviews and observations show that nurses need leaders who are caring,

empathetic, have charisma and provide protection. There is a significant positive relationship between the effectiveness of training and teamwork together with the performance of nurses. Nurses need training to increase competence in working in accordance with the progress of the development of the world of health. On the other hand, nurses stated the importance of teamwork in improving service performance. Nurses stated that the effectiveness of the training is determined if the training is in accordance with what is expected by nurses, namely fun training with the latest training materials.

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